

HIPPARCOS

Effective dead time due to veiling glare

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Introduction

'Veiling glare' refers to light scattering inside the IDT, whereby some fraction of any light falling anywhere on the photocathode will be picked up by the IFOV. Veiling glare produced by a bright star is of course modulated by the grid and may therefore cause phase errors in the measurements of faint stars somewhere else in the field.

If the piloting strategy does not take this effect into account when scheduling the stars for observation, some measurements on the fainter stars will inevitably be lost ('dead time'). This note gives some estimates of the fractional dead times expected from this phenomenon. Some possible remedies, including light-curve analysis similar to that for double stars, are also discussed.

Fractional dead time for a given pair

Consider a pair of stars separated by the angle r . Let M and m be their magnitudes, $M < m$. If r is less than the diagonal of the FOV, it will sometimes happen that both stars are inside the FOV, in which case it may be difficult or impossible to observe the fainter one, depending on the magnitude difference and the intensity of the veiling glare. We shall assume that observation of the faint star is prohibited if the veiling glare exceeds a certain fraction (f) of its intensity. In practice we may have $f \sim 0.02$. This situation will occur more often, the closer the pair and the smaller the magnitude difference. Given that M , m , and r are such that f is likely to be exceeded whenever both stars are in the FOV simultaneously, the question is: at a time when the faint star is inside the FOV, what is the probability that also the bright star is inside the FOV?

This probability (P) is easily obtained as a function only of the ratio $\rho = r/w$ ($w =$ width and length of FOV) under the assumptions:

- (i) that the FOV is a square with sides = w ;
- (ii) that the direction of scanning with respect to the line connecting the pair, θ , is uniformly distributed in $[0, 2\pi[$;
- (iii) that the field centre is uniformly and independently distributed in both coordinates with respect to the faint star. Then

$$P(\rho) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \left[1 - \min(1, \rho|\sin \theta|) \right] \left[1 - \min(1, \rho|\sin \theta|) \right] d\theta$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{1}{\pi} \rho(4 - \rho) & \text{for } 0 \leq \rho \leq 1 \\ 1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \left[\frac{\rho^2 + 2}{4} + \arctan(\rho^2 - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} - (\rho^2 - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] & \text{for } 1 \leq \rho \leq \sqrt{2} \\ 0 & \text{for } \sqrt{2} \leq \rho \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

See Fig. 1. It can be noted that P is quite small (< 5 %) for $\rho > 1$, i.e. for $r > w$.

The inverse of the function $P(\rho)$ shall be called $\rho(P)$. Thus the fractional dead time on a given star is likely to exceed P if there is a bright enough star within a radius of $w\rho(P)$. The probability that this is the case is calculated next.

Probability of finding a bright star inside a radius R

If μ is the expected number of bright stars within a circle of radius R, then according to the Poisson distribution, the probability is

$$S = 1 - \exp(-\mu) \quad (2)$$

that at least one such star is inside the circle. 'Bright' means here brighter than

$$M(r) = m + 2.5 \lg[a(r)/f] \quad (3)$$

where $a(r)$, $0 \leq r \leq R$ is the veiling glare attenuation as function of offset

angle (r). Let $D(M)$ be the areal density (on the sky) of stars brighter than M . We have then

$$\mu = 2 \int_0^R D[M(r)] 2\pi r dr \quad (4)$$

where the factor 2 comes from superpositioning two fields. Thus,

$$S = 1 - \exp\left[-4\pi \int_0^R D[m - 2.5 \lg f + 2.5 \lg a(r)] r dr\right] \quad (5)$$

If $R = w\phi(P)$, then $S(m, P)$ is the probability that the fractional dead time on a star of magnitude m exceeds P . The expected fractional dead time is

$$T(m) = E[S(m, P)] = - \int_0^1 \frac{dS}{dP} P dP \quad (6)$$

Evaluation of $S(m, P)$ and $T(m)$

From measurements of veiling glare it appears that $a(r)$ is fairly accurately represented by the function

$$a(r) = a_0 [1 + (r/r_0)^2]^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where $r_0 \approx 0.40 \text{ mm} \approx 0.037^\circ$ and $a_0 \approx 0.012(q_H/q_W)^2$. q_H and q_W are the IFOV diameters for HIPPARCOS and as used in the Wisconsin report (MAT-HIP-00617).

From Allen, *Astrophysical Quantities* (1973, p.243) we have for the relevant magnitude interval,

$$D(M) \approx \text{dex}(-3.85 + 0.45M) = \exp(\alpha + \beta M) \quad [\text{deg}^{-2}] \quad (8)$$

with $\alpha = -3.85(\ln 10) \approx -8.865$, $\beta = 0.45(\ln 10) \approx 1.036$. Introducing (8) and (7) in (5), we obtain

$$S(m, P) = 1 - \exp\left\{-2D(m) \pi r_0^2 \frac{(a_0/f)^{\gamma\beta}}{\gamma\beta - 1} \left[1 - [1 + (R/r_0)^2]^{1-\gamma\beta}\right]\right\} \quad (9)$$

where $\gamma \equiv 2.5 \lg e \approx 1.086$. $T(m)$ is best obtained by numerical integration of (6).

With $w/r_0 \approx 25$ and $\gamma\beta \approx 1.125$ we have more concisely,

$$S(m, P) = 1 - \exp\left\{-A \left[1 - [1 + 125 \rho^2(P)]^{-0.125}\right]\right\} \quad (10)$$

where

$$A(m) = 16 D(m) \pi r_0^2 (a_0/f)^{1.125} \quad (11)$$

In particular,

$$S(m, 0.75) = 1 - \exp(-0.206 A) \quad (12)$$

Figure 2 shows $S(m, P)$ for $a_0 = 0.005$, $f = 0.02$, and $D(m)$ according to (8). Since $S(m, P)$ depends on m only through $A(m)$, eqn (11) can be used to translate the Figure to any other combination of a_0 , f , and $D(m)$.

The table below shows $T(m)$ = expected dead time, $S(m, .75)$ = probability that the dead time exceeds 75 %, $U(m)\Delta m$ = percentage observing time spent on the different magnitudes (ITT, IA, p.40), and $T(m)U(m)\Delta m$ adding up to the total mission dead time due to veiling glare.

m	A(m)	T(m)	S(m, .75)	U(m)Δm	T(m)U(m)Δm
8.0	0.008	0.002	0.002	-----	
8.5	0.014	0.004	0.003	0.33	0.0013
9.0	0.023	0.007	0.005	-----	
9.5	0.039	0.011	0.008	0.18	0.0020
10.0	0.065	0.019	0.013	-----	
10.5	0.11	0.031	0.022	0.18	0.0056
11.0	0.18	0.052	0.036	-----	
11.5	0.31	0.086	0.062	0.12	0.0103
12.0	0.51	0.139	0.100	-----	
12.5	0.86	0.220	0.162	0.06	0.0132
13.0	1.5	0.335	0.266	-----	
13.5	2.4	0.484	0.390	0.00	0.0000
TOTAL:					0.0324

Remedies?

From the mission point of view, the effects of veiling glare are marginal: even without any counteraction the total 'dead time' is less than 4 %. For a given faint star (say $m = 12.5$) the situation is different however: the expected dead time is 22 % and there is even a 16 % risk that the dead time exceeds 75 % (which would double the mean errors on that star). That there is a non-negligible risk of getting very high fractional dead times is a consequence of the relative flatness of the curves in Fig. 2, and reflects the simple fact that if a bright star happens to be close on the sky to the star in question (within some 0.4°), then most observations of it will be disturbed.

The situation is therefore unsatisfactory with respect to the faintest programme stars which, although few in number, may be particularly interesting, carefully handpicked objects. It may be very troublesome near the galactic plane or in open clusters. What can be done?

- (a) No action: accept some degradation and even the complete loss of some objects.
- (b) Hardware improvement: reduce veiling glare intensity (a_0), which would reduce $S(m, P)$ and $T(m)$ roughly in proportion. Even a factor 2 would be a big improvement!
- (c) Programme constraints: avoid programme stars close to brighter stars, cf. eqn (3).
- (d) Observational constraints: avoid observing a faint star while there is also a bright star in the FOV. This requires some (possibly complicated) modification of the on-board observing sequence generator. The method may be efficient when the disturbing star is rather distant from the faint star ($r > 0.5^\circ$) or when it belongs to the other FOV; in other cases the 'permitted' observing time may be very restricted and the measurements tend to be made only near the FOV edges and asymmetrically with respect to the field centre. This last effect is perhaps dangerous in view of systematic error sources (chromaticity etc).
- (e) A posteriori correction: eliminate phase errors in the scientific data analysis. This is further investigated below.

A posteriori correction

The modulation component produced by veiling glare is very similar to that from a faint companion star in the IFOV, so it would seem that the methods that will be used for detection and reduction of double stars could also be useful here. Compared with the double stars, the present problem even seems to be much simpler because

- (i) there is no detection problem: the presence of a bright star in the FOV is most likely known;
- (ii) the phase of the veiling glare component is known, usually better than what can be obtained for the faint star.

Thus, only the intensity of the veiling glare component need to be determined.

The effects of the extra component can be studied by means of the following simplified model. Let $g(\psi) \equiv 1 + M_1 \cos \psi + M_2 \cos 2\psi$ be the response function of a unit intensity centred point source. For a single, undisturbed star, the intensity model would be

$$I_0(\psi) = a_1 + a_2 g(\psi + a_3) \quad (13)$$

where a_1 = background intensity, a_2 = object intensity, a_3 = object phase. In presence of veiling glare with known phase ($\Delta\psi$) but unknown intensity (a_4), the signal model would be

$$I_1(\psi) = a_1 + a_2 g(\psi + a_3) + a_4 g(\psi + \Delta\psi) \quad (14)$$

Let us first assume that there is no veiling glare, so (13) represents the true situation and is also used for maximum likelihood estimation of a_3 . This estimate ($\hat{a}_3$) is of course unbiased and its mean error can be estimated from the Cramer-Rao bound,

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{a}}) = \left[\int \left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial \underline{a}} \right)^t \frac{\partial I}{\partial \underline{a}} \frac{d\psi}{I(\psi)} \right]^{-1} \quad (15)$$

where $\underline{a} \equiv (a_1 \ a_2 \ a_3)^t$.

Then suppose that veiling glare is present, so (14) represents the true situation, but (13) is still used as signal model. The resulting estimate a_3^* is in general biased, $b \equiv E(a_3^* - a_3) \neq 0$. The bias can be obtained

(approximately) by formally making a maximum likelihood fit of a_1, a_2, a_3 to $I_1(\psi)$. The resulting phase bias will depend on $f \equiv a_4/a_2$ and $\Delta\psi$ as shown in Fig. 3. For given f , the maximum bias is found for $\Delta\psi \approx \pm 70^\circ$, viz.

$$|b|_{\max} \approx 0''.137 f \quad (16)$$

E.g. $f = 0.02$ gives $|b| \lesssim 2.8$ mas.

Let us finally assume that (14) is used for estimating a_3 in presence (or absence) of veiling glare. The result is of course unbiased, but the solution is weakened by the extra unknown (a_4), so the rms error on a_3 will be higher than in the first case, eqn (15). The Cramer-Rao bound can again be used to compute the rms error as in (15), now with $\underline{a} \equiv (a_1 \ a_2 \ a_3 \ a_4)^t$. The ratio,

$$[\text{rms error of } a_3 \text{ from (14)}] \div [\text{rms error of } a_3 \text{ from (13)}] \geq 1 \quad (17)$$

depends on f and $\Delta\psi$ as shown in Fig. 4. It is clear that the method could work also in highly contaminated cases, e.g. $f = 0.3$, but only if $|\Delta\psi| \gtrsim 90^\circ$. Thus, light-curve analysis (with unknown a_4) is virtually useless in about half of the disturbed cases.

The situation would be very different if also a_4 (or f) was known a priori. E.g. if a_4 is known to about $\pm 10\%$, then one could probably allow $f \leq 0.2$, which would reduce the effective dead time by a factor 10. The rms error degradation would then be mostly due to the increased background count rate (while its modulation would be unimportant), and would amount to about 10% for $f = 0.2$, roughly independent of $\Delta\psi$. The feasibility of calibrating veiling glare to $\pm 10\%$ appears very questionable in view of the huge number of calibration points (10^6 for a 30×30 point mesh!). The alternative, to measure it in real time interlaced with the measurements on the faint star, would require considerable observing time (e.g. 2.5 s for $f = 0.2$, $m = 12$), so we end up again with lots of dead time!

Conclusions

Veiling glare is a problem for the faintest stars. A posteriori correction will be of some help but cannot eliminate the problem. Accurate calibration of the glare may be desirable. The observing programme (Input Catalogue) and the observing strategy will most likely have to be constrained.

FIGURE 1. $P(\rho)$ = probability that both stars in a pair are inside the FOV, given that one star is, as function of normalized separation r/w (w = width and length of FOV).

$S(m, P)$

FIGURE 2. $S(m, P)$ = probability that the fractional dead time on a star of magnitude m exceeds P .

Assumptions: $a_0 = 0.005$, $f = 0.02$, $D(m) = \text{dex}(-3.85 + 0.45m)$ stars per deg^2 .

positional
bias (b)

[mas]

FIGURE 3. Bias caused by veiling glare out of phase with the modulated faint star. $\Delta\psi$ = phase difference on first harmonic ($180^\circ = 0.6$ arcsec displacement), f = veiling glare intensity/faint star intensity. Assumptions: $s = 1.2''$, $M_1 = 0.69$, $M_2 = 0.29$, background count rate = 100 Hz, faint star count rate = 274 Hz ($m = 12$).

N.B. vertical scale is 0 - 200 mas for $f = 0.3$ and 1 (dashed curves).

relative positional
rms error

FIGURE 4. Increase of rms error when the veiling glare intensity is estimated along with the three usual parameters for the faint star (background level, position and intensity).

Assumptions: same as in Fig. 3.